

INTERACTIVE APPROACHES IN TEACHING

Aripova Elena Azizovna

Senior Lecturer WIUT

earipova@wiut.uz**Kim Igor Lavrentevich**

Lecturer WIUT

i.kim@wiut.uz**Surkov Dmitry Yurevich**

Lecturer WIUT

dsurkov2@wiut.uz**Аннотация**

В статье обсуждаются причины необходимости применения игр в преподавании математики. Это исследование носит эмпирический и описательный характер, его результаты предлагают некоторые практические решения, которые могут быть применены

Annotation

The article goes over the benefits of using games to teach math. This study's methodology is empirical and descriptive, and its findings offer solutions that can be used in the classroom.

Ключевые слова:

Онлайн-обучение, игры, интерактивные подходы.

Keywords:

E-learning, quizzes and gaming activities, interactive methods.

INTERACTIVE APPROACHES IN TEACHING

Introduction

There is disagreement among educators and academic institutions regarding the best ways to integrate cutting-edge methodologies and technologies into the classroom. However, the goal of gaming in education is to increase students' motivation and engagement, improve students' visual skills, improve students' interaction and collaboration abilities with their peers, and allow students to apply gaming values to real-world situations. Gaming in education may be perceived as a barrier to learning. Technology in education has been heavily utilized to streamline and enhance learning ever since the first wave of the COVID 19 lockdown. To be effective, technological tools must be in line with the curriculum, so this does not immediately affect student achievement. This research investigates the implementation and use of gaming apps within an online instructional setting.

It is well known that playing games calls for participants to follow a set of rules. According to (Houghton, 2013), educational games are used to support the teaching and learning process. In order to improve the learning experience for students and teach additional skills like rule-following, adaptability, problem-solving, interaction, critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and good sportsmanship, games can be used as a supplemental tool to augment traditional teaching techniques. Games can be used as an additional teaching tool to supplement traditional teaching methods and improve the learning experience for students. Learning shouldn't be a chore, and it shouldn't just be rote memorization exercises that students must complete in order to memorize information for tests. Learning that is improved by technology may bring a sense of vibrancy and creative thinking to the classroom, which can be beneficial to instructors as they work to improve student accomplishment.

Educational institutions, schools, and families all make use of a variety of educational game formats. The main goal of using games in the classroom is to help students develop their critical thinking abilities while studying a particular subject by

challenging them to be creative while following the rules. Other games are available that are focused on improving knowledge in a particular subject, with math games being the most popular of these. Despite the fact that games like chess help players improve their critical-thinking abilities and other educationally necessary skills, according to Yue and Zin (2009), they cannot be regarded as educational because they do not transmit content or communicate curriculum information. Games that feature educational content or other educational games are considered instructional games.

Lengeling and Malarche (2007) describe the benefits as follows:

Affective:

- The emotional filters are removed while playing games.
- They encourage the creative, free-flowing use of language.
- They also improve their communication skills.
- Games are entertaining and inspiring.

Cognitive: Playing games makes studying easier.

As a result, learning is strengthened and expanded.

It is important that communicative language is emphasized in games.

The focus of games is primarily on the students, with the teacher serving only as an intermediary. Games also foster class unity and may increase participation overall. They also foster friendly competition between students.

Adaptability:

Each of the four talents is utilized in these games, which are adaptable in terms of their complexity, level, and target audience. The least amount of preparation is required for games once the first development phase is finished.

In light of these characteristics, teachers may be encouraged to adopt games to help students practice language in the classroom. Games can be used to teach, and when done properly, they can even make learning enjoyable. One of the most crucial things students can do to make sure they are learning the material required for any given course, semester, or even individual session is to go through the syllabus and finish the

assigned work. The games shouldn't get in the way of this at all. It is essential that they be used as a tool rather than developing a will of their own and acting independently. After the fundamental information of a given session has been provided and understood, as well as after exercises that practice and apply the new language, games may then be offered as an additional way for fostering deeper comprehension.

Researchers Bourgonjon and colleagues found that when it comes to implementing pedagogical strategies at educational institutions, educators are viewed as the "real change agents." (2013, p. 30). Nearly none of the teachers had ever played video games themselves, according to research done to determine how instructors felt about their use in the classroom. Even though only 9.4% of teachers actually use video games in the classroom, 77.5% of teachers believe that playing video games can help students learn. Lack of time, installing the game, and configuring PCs are all problems that teachers encounter when implementing games. A global survey was conducted by Egenfeldt-Nielsen et al. (2011) with 275 primary and middle school teachers from the United States, Finland, Norway, Sweden and Portugal. Regarding their experiences utilizing games in language learning, the teachers were questioned. According to many of the study's participants, support and training in pertinent areas are necessary for teachers to use games effectively. The survey's results indicate that almost 60% of all teachers use games in the classroom. A study was conducted in Sweden by Mathe (2020, page 59) to find out how teachers felt about the issues raised by online gaming. The majority of the lecturers—about two thirds—had used digital gaming in the classroom at some point, for a variety of subject matter. The majority of educators feel confident utilizing digital games in their lessons and are interested in incorporating them, despite the fact that many of them do not have any personal interest in gaming.

Bourgonjon et al. looked into the attitudes of 858 secondary school students toward online gaming. (2010, page 1145) Male students are more inclined to use video games in the classroom than female students, who are less inclined to do so. The majority of students believe that some video games might be educational (Bourgonjon

et al., 2010, p. 1149). It is impossible to categorize certain student groups as a single gaming community due to the fact that they do not participate in the practice of playing digital games. The authors recommend incorporating a variety of games into the educational setting in light of the findings. (Bourgonjon et al., 2010, p. 1152).

Mifsud et al. (2013) investigated the attitudes of students, instructors, and parents concerning the use of video games in the classroom as well as the influence that these games have on students' ability to learn English as a second language at four secondary schools in Malta. The authors conducted a survey with students to gather information on the educational potential of digital games in the classroom as well as how students actually utilized games in the classroom (Mifsud et al., 2013, p. 37). According to the data, the vast majority of the 1,441 students (79.1%) are excited about the prospect of adopting digital games in the classroom since these games may assist them in developing their English abilities (Mifsud et al. 2013, p. 48).

Erkkila (2017) investigates the perspectives of 779 Finnish students towards digital games and what they believe they may learn from playing them for the purpose of improving their skills. The majority of the students are in the higher grade levels. Although the majority of students feel that game-acquired language enhances their performance in the classroom and makes learning simpler, there are a few students who hold the contrary belief (Erkkila, 2017, p. 72). Playing games, according to a number of students, increased their motivation to learn. The students also said that playing games increased their excitement in learning. 592 students said that playing computer games enhanced their education at school. While 339 students said that learning via games was not very beneficial or just slightly helpful, 241 students thought that it was very helpful or a big assistance (Erkkila, 2017, p. 72).

Interviews were conducted with a total of 21 students from Botkyrka High School by Wiklund and Gilbert (2005). Each of the 21 students believes that they can learn on their own without an instructor's help by playing computer games on a regular basis.

Students believe that playing video games will improve their understanding of class material. (Wiklund & Glimbert, 2005, p. 1).

In addition to teaching, educational games also heavily rely on engagement. The role of video gaming in schools in comparison to other activities is examined by Groff et al. (2012). The game, according to both the students and the teachers, was more engaging and inspiring than previous teaching strategies. (Marklund, 2015, p. 125).

Prensky claims that playing video games can bring about feelings of joy, a deep and passionate level of engagement, structure, motivation, and learning, as well as adrenaline, creativity, social groups, and emotion. (2007, p. 144). He claims that the method uses an interactive learning strategy and also adds interest, which is why he thinks learning through digital games is effective. This depends on the established learning objectives. Align the learner and the content. If not, no technique will ever lead to learning. (Prensky, 2007, p. 147)

Researchers Egenfeldt-Nielsen and colleagues assert that playing video games enhances students' subject-matter knowledge, skills, and attitudes. He thinks that playing games while learning is a more effective and entertaining strategy. (Egenfeldt-Nielsen et al., 2011, p. 32). A survey was carried out by Egenfeldt-Nielsen et al. (2011) with 275 teachers from the United States, Finland, Norway, and Portugal. Only 12% of teachers, according to the authors, believe that using games as a teaching strategy can help students become motivated and engaged. (Egenfeldt-Nielsen et al., 2011, p. 193).

A summary of the findings from a variety of academic publications that have undergone peer review was put together by Yu et al. (2020, page 4). According to Yu et al.'s analysis of empirical studies, contextual game-based learning enhances students' attitudes, levels of motivation, and critical thinking skills in addition to their academic performance. (2020, page 11). By incorporating learning strategies like game-based learning, collaborative learning, and context-aware learning while playing educational games, students' academic performance may be enhanced. To increase the educational

value of games, put an emphasis on interactions between the game, the player, and the environment. Researchers Yu et al. and Mifsud et al. (2013) looked into the advantages and disadvantages of using videogames in the classroom. When compared to the control group (CG), the experimental group (EG) demonstrated significant improvements. (Mifsud et al., 2013, p. 32). The game used in the experiment provided practice in a wide variety of secondary school language courses (Mifsud et al., p. 39). The teachers felt that the game's linguistic goals were a good fit for the English curriculum that they were teaching to their students (Mifsud et al., 2007).

Ho (2020) studied Chinese university students who were taking English-language courses. Ho discovered that incorporating digital games with active learning techniques like narrative development and storytelling had a positive effect on students' capacity to learn. She claimed that game-based learning increased "behavioral, cognitive, and motivational participation." According to her research, playing video games to learn a language may boost academic interest, reduce anxiety, and encourage communication. (Ho, 2020, pp. 432-433).

The observation described here was made at the pre-university department of the Westminster International University in Tashkent. The department's main goal is to get secondary school students ready for their bachelor's-level college studies.

Pre-foundation students received their education online during the lockdown, so the teachers used some of the Internet's educational game tools to make the lessons more engaging for the kids. The tools that were used successfully to teach math in English and go over the material that was covered are listed below.

Using Google Forms Google Forms is one of the free resources that can be used to assess the level of knowledge held by students enrolled in online classes. Since the instructor only needs to type in the questions and answers, it is easy to use. The remaining tasks are finished automatically and on their own. When it is all said and done, and the students have turned in their answers, they will be able to acquire answers along with explanations. This makes it easier for the instructor to do their job. In

addition, "Google Forms" provides the opportunity to create questionnaires, which may be used to collect feedback from students.

2.Kahoot. (<https://kahoot.com>)

When taking online classes, Kahoot, a popular website, can be helpful for studying. One of the most crucial factors to take into account when looking for online classroom games is how simple it is for both students and teachers to use the platform. Use of the Kahoot website is free; all you need to do is sign up to gain access to more features and connect with more students.

Your students might use their smartphones to take part in Kahoot games when you share the screen. It is a great tool for classroom settings because students will be competing against one another to win. There are games for beginners, games about Cambridge, games with Disney or Star Wars themes, and games with current events as the focus for more experienced students. Users of any age or skill level can use it. Each multiple-choice question gives students ten, twenty, or thirty seconds to respond, making it a useful tool for students to review material and gauge their level of understanding. This is a fantastic way to test students' prior knowledge while introducing them to a new topic.

Although it is generally agreed that using games to teach students new material is an effective method, planning and supervising these activities can take a lot of the teacher's time and effort. Additionally, the vast majority of students enjoy playing competitive video games. The use of games in the classroom was not well received by a subgroup of students who felt inadequate while playing games because they were matched against strong opponents.

Despite the fact that there are no games included in the book, Maths teachers nevertheless make use of games in their lessons since they are aware of the positive impact that games have on their students. To summarize, playing games is an efficient way to teach, although, the fact that it requires a lot of preparation work and may be physically demanding for the teacher.

Because teaching a foreign language requires a significant investment of both time and effort, it is something that should be given significant thought. On the basis of the findings of this survey, the following recommendations may be made:

- Teachers should pay more attention to students who are uninterested in the activity, and games should be adjusted appropriately.
- There should be additional time built into each class period for teachers to go over game tactics and finish up lesson preparations.
- Educators could sometimes organize games to be played in locations other than the classroom.

Students of the BaQS module on the CPFS course typically experienced excitement and elevated curiosity when first exposed to the Kahoot interactive testing tool because it was a new experience for the majority of students. Students were seen to be generally much more focused on the subject that was included in the game, even those who had previously occasionally had trouble paying attention. A lot of pop culture references were used throughout the game, which was presented as multiple-choice questions so that students could more easily relate to it. When math concepts are explained using pop culture allusions, students tend to feel much more at ease because they perceive the material as more approachable and appealing than when it is presented in purely scientific terms. This is largely because of their age and the fact that it's crucial to maintain focus in order to understand math concepts, which is made simpler when there are some relatable examples they can make connections with.

The games were designed so that students had to form small groups of three, give those groups names, and then respond to math questions within set time limits. They had to do that while keeping in mind that they were competing with other students and that the quicker they provided the right answer, the more points they would receive. Students found it to be exciting and stimulating, and success in the game required accuracy and speed.

Such a structure has sparked a spirit of competition that has in turn led to the process of accessing some pertinent information from earlier topics. Students typically exhibit some reluctance when required to constantly refresh their memories of prior material. Students were eagerly trying to recall some previously studied concepts, though, and were successfully doing that thanks to their naturally competitive spirits that the game triggered. This interactive experience made students much more aware of the value of reviewing and reinforcing previously learned material, which was a major accomplishment.

Students who have experienced this style of instruction have grown accustomed to the "fun" aspect of their regular math classes and have begun to show great interest and anticipation for future opportunities. Students have shown a stronger desire to understand subjects and have begun to address questions about some math concepts they have previously studied but had a shaky grasp on while aware that it awaits them and will soon be played again. As the tool accumulates points and each time it is used, students become more prepared and try to respond to questions as quickly as possible, students were eager to outsmart their classmates from other teams.

A series of questions from earlier and more recent times were used to create those quizzes. They were interspersed with jokes and humorous references, which greatly enhanced the process' authenticity and piqued students' interest.

There are some things that you need to think about and be cautious of. It is crucial to have a solid understanding of each student and to be sensitive to and supportive of those who are more reserved than the others. This is crucial because, when playing such games in groups, some students have a tendency to withdraw and remain outside of the contentious debates while attempting to answer quiz questions. Within those small groups, it was noticed that there was always a leader who dominated the activity and occasionally did so aggressively. While this is generally advantageous for students who are in charge and taking charge of the group, it is less advantageous for those who are left out due to a lack of assertiveness in character. It is crucial to be aware of these circumstances and to foster a positive environment where, ideally, everyone participates in discussion and decisions are made alternately. Additionally, if there aren't many students in attendance, it's sometimes a good idea to play this game with each player individually, where there are no groups and everyone makes their own decisions.

Bibliography:

1. Bourgonjon, J., Valcke, M., Soetaert, R., Schellens, T. 2010. Students' perception about the use of video games in the classroom. *Computers & Education*, vol. 54, no.4, pp. 1145-1156.
2. Bourgonjon, J., De Grove, F., De Smet, C., Van Looy, J., Soetaert, R., & Valcke, M.
3. 2013. Acceptance of game-based learning by secondary school teachers.
4. *Computers & Education*, vol. 67, pp. 21-35.
5. Egenfeldt-Nielsen, S., Meyer, B., & Holm Sørensen, B. 2011. *Serious Games in Education – A Global Perspective [E-book]*. Copenhagen: Aarhus University Press.
6. Erkkilä, M. 2017. *Learning English from Digital Games: Finnish upper secondary school students' perspective on game-enhanced language learning*. Helsinki:

University of Jyväskylä.

7. Groff, J., Howells, C. and Cranmer, S. 2012. "Console Game-Based Pedagogy: A Study of Primary and Secondary Classroom Learning through Console Video Games", *International Journal of Game-Based Learning*, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp 35-54.

8. Ho, J. 2020. Gamifying the flipped classroom: how to motivate Chinese ESL learners? *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching*, 14:5, 421-436, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17501229.2019.1614185>.

9. Houghton, E., Aston, H., Featherstone, G., Perrotta, C., Houghton, E., & Aston, H. et al. (2013). Game-based

10. learning: Latest evidence and future directions. Slough: NFER.: (NFER Research Programme:

11. Innovation in Education). Retrieved from <https://www.nfer.ac.uk/publications/GAME01>

12. Lengeling, M. and Malarcher, C., 1997. Index Cards: A Natural Resource for Teachers. 'Forum', October – December 1997., Vol. 35(No 4), p. Page 42.

13. Mathe, M. 2020. Mapping the Landscape of Digital Game-Based Learning in Swedish Compulsory and Upper-Secondary Schools – Opportunities and Challenges for Teachers [Doctoral dissertation thesis] Report Series, Department of Computer and System Sciences, Stockholm University.

14. Mifsud, C., Vella, R. & Camilleri, L. 2013. Attitudes towards and effects of the use of video games in classroom learning with specific reference to literacy attainment. *Research in Education*, 90(1), 32-52. <https://doi.org/10.7227%2FRIE.90.1.3>.

15. Prensky, M. 2007. "Why Education and Training Have Not Changed". In *Digital Game-Based Learning*, McGraw-Hill.

16. Sundqvist, P., & Wikström, P. 2015. Out-of-school digital gameplay and in-school L2 English vocabulary outcomes. *System*, 51, pp. 65–76.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2015.04.001>

17. Sylvén, L. K. 2013. CLIL in Sweden – Why does it not work? A Metaperspective on CLIL across contexts in Europe. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 16(3), pp 301-320. doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2013.777387

18. Wiklund, M., & Glimbert, L. Students perception of a learning environment and the teachers role while using unmodified computer games as learning tools in upper secondary education. Department of Computer and Systems Sciences. Stockholm University.

19. Yu, Z., Gao, M., & Wang, L. 2020. The effect of educational games on learning outcomes, student motivation, engagement and satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*. 1(1) pp 1-25. doi.org/10.1177/0735633120969214.

20. Xu, Z., Chen, Z., Eutsler, L., Geng, Z., & Kogut, A. 2020. A scoping review of digital game-based technology on English language learning. *Education Tech Research*. 68(3), pp. 877-904. doi.org/10.1007/s11423-019-09702-2.

21. Yue, W., & Zin, N. (2009). History educational games design. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE).